

Compact Multichannel Plasmonic Device for Rapid and Versatile Inflammatory Biomarker Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Plasmonic biosensors have demonstrated versatility across diverse applications, including clinical diagnostics, environmental monitoring, and food analysis. Multiplexed plasmonic biosensors capable of detecting multiple analytes simultaneously have also been developed. However, existing designs face challenges for wide-scale adoption due to bulky designs and expense. We present a compact multichannel plasmonic biosensor platform for multiplexed detection of up to four biomarkers from one sample distributed via microfluidic channels. The device operates under the Kretschmann configuration for sequential quasi-simultaneous multichannel sensing. Optical performance evaluation demonstrates high sensitivity and a limit of detection (LOD) of 10^{-6} RIU across four channels. The biosensing capabilities of the device have been assessed for detecting four inflammatory biomarkers. Customized biofunctionalization of sensor chips ensures inter-channel reproducibility and direct binding detection assays for C-reactive protein (CRP), interleukin-6 (IL-6), procalcitonin (PCT), and pancreatic stone protein (PSP), with sensitivities in the low ng/mL range and negligible cross-reactivity. Recovery testing confirms its feasibility for detecting multiple biomarkers at low concentrations in human serum. The compact, user-friendly design makes this biosensor an attractive tool for multiplexed detection, underscoring its applicability beyond inflammatory-related processes, offering a versatile solution for biomarker analysis in human fluids and contributing to the decentralization of diagnostics for complex diseases.

KEYWORDS: Plasmonic biosensor, multiplexed detection, point-of-care device, microfluidics; inflammation; sepsis biomarkers

1. Introduction

Plasmonic sensing has become an effective and widely used technique to explore biomolecular interactions in real time. Its underlying physical principle enables rapid detection and non-destructive, label-free monitoring [1–5]. These properties have made plasmonic sensing a key technology in optical biosensors and have promoted its use in clinical diagnostics. Plasmonic biosensors have been designed with different configurations to maximize their sensitivity and meet the requirements for point-of-care (POC) use, in terms of operability (integration and user-friendliness), size, and cost. The needs of modern clinical diagnostics, however, have evolved, shifting towards a personalized, patient-centered approach, which demands a more comprehensive understanding of the patient status. This places additional requirements on new diagnostic tools, which often translate into the need for simultaneous detection and quantification of multiple parameters or biomarkers. A key example is in the monitoring of complex inflammatory processes in critical care patients, where measuring multiple biomarkers simultaneously is crucial to obtaining the full understanding of immune dysregulation, enabling early diagnosis, stratification of disease severity and guiding targeted interventions.

Inflammation is a natural immune response to infections, injuries, or toxins, which aims to heal the body. It can manifest as chronic inflammation [6], leading to conditions such as asthma, arthritis, or inflammatory bowel diseases, or acute inflammation [7], commonly due to current bacterial or viral infections. Inflammatory processes involve the release of proteins, including cytokines and antibodies [8–11]. Early diagnosis of acute inflammation is crucial to provide timely treatment and improve survival rates, especially in uncontrolled infections that may lead to severe complications like cytokine storm syndrome or sepsis [12–15]. Inflammation biomarkers like C-reactive protein (CRP), fibrinogen, and lactate are well-established in

clinical practice in addition to leukocyte count and differentiation. Procalcitonin (PCT) has become the gold standard biomarker for early identification of sepsis and is used to guide antibiotic treatment duration in clinically relevant bacterial infections. Interleukins (IL), such as IL-6, IL-8, IL-18, play an essential role in regulating immune responses and are relevant inflammatory biomarkers. The combined simultaneous detection of multiple inflammatory biomarkers can provide a comprehensive view of the patient's immune status, thus enabling faster differentiation between infection types (*i.e.* bacterial or viral), a better disease severity assessment, and an overall more personalized and prognostic clinical decision. In this regard, inflammatory biomarkers are analyzed frequently in hospitalized patients to monitor the evolution of their levels, once a treatment plan has been established. However, analyzing these biomarkers is typically performed in centralized laboratory settings with immunoassays like ELISA (enzyme-linked immune-sorbent assay), CLIA (chemiluminescent immunoassay), or immunohistochemistry. The analyses are commonly done individually for each biomarker, in any case requiring time for collection, sample analysis, and processing, and result delivery back to the clinic. This sequential workflow can often delay treatment decisions or make the results less relevant due to patient's evolving clinical status. These limitations underscore the pressing need for efficient point-of-care devices capable of providing rapid, multiplexed quantitative analyses in decentralized settings, like Intensive Care Units (ICU) or medium-sized clinics, which are often less equipped in terms of centralized laboratory infrastructures. Ideally, such a test should be available as a POC device, and: i) have a short turnaround analysis (time-to-result < 30 min), ii) provide sensitive and quantitative evaluation of the biomarkers levels, iii) be repeatable frequently, iv) be close to the patient to minimize sample manipulation, transport needs, and delay in the results, and v) provide a combined analysis of several biomarkers to increase specificity and accuracy of the results.

Plasmonic biosensors are attractive candidates for such a device, but need to evolve, to be able to provide compact systems that maintain their excellent sensing performance across multiple targets. Simultaneous measurements, however, remain challenging due to technological aspects of the illumination and detection optics, the design of the microfluidic sample cartridges, and the specialized biofunctionalization required for multiple detection. This has so far prevented their use in clinical diagnostics despite various attempts. Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) imaging provides high-throughput detection of tens of analytes usually through an array-based [16]. However, SPR imaging is challenged with cost, size, and sensitivity, generally requiring high-performance expensive, and bulky imaging systems. Multianalyte capabilities have also been reported using localized SPR (LSPR) [17,18], which foregoes the need for optical coupling elements, but at the expense of costly detection instrumentation and complex microfluidic systems to control sample injection. Advances in plasmonic biosensors have enabled compact, multiplexed platforms through the integration of multi-channel and multi-parameter SPR configurations and refined microfluidic architectures[19,20]. Four to eight multichannel designs have been described using grating coupled plasmonic sensors [21] or using Kretschmann illumination configuration [22–24] but mainly employing expensive CCD cameras to detect the output signal. Microfluidic designs for such sensors commonly use individual channels with isolated inlets and outlets, which, while being appropriate for multisampling, can complicate the fluidic design and performance. Commercial systems such as Reichert® SPR (4-channels), MP-SPR NAVI™ (2-channels), and Biacore™ 8 series (8-channels) illustrate the potential of these approaches, combining sensitivity, parallelism, and precision (despite their high cost) for both research and clinical use, although commonly with bulky designs. Multiplexing can be achieved by splitting a single sample injection into multiple parallel channels or by using independently addressable flow paths, where both multi-channel and multiplex detection modes can be combined [25–27].

Here, we present a compact and affordable configuration for a multichannel plasmonic biosensor with a multiplexed architecture for the simultaneous detection of a panel of relevant inflammatory biomarkers from a single sample. We have selected CRP, PCT, and IL-6 as biomarkers for their demonstrated relevance in inflammatory processes [13–15,28] as well as pancreatic stone protein (PSP), an emerging biomarker gaining attention for its superior accuracy compared to CPR and PCT [29–31]. CRP increases its blood concentration rapidly (below 3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to higher than 150 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) upon stimulation by pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-6 [13–15]. IL-6 is a cytokine protein typically presented in concentrations below 15 pg/mL which rises to over 3 ng/mL in septic patients [14,15]. PCT is a peptide prohormone of calcitonin that is not detectable in healthy individuals, and its levels spike to over 2 ng/mL within hours of disease onset in response to pro-inflammatory stimuli [14,15,29]. Although PSP's precise role remains unclear, it seems that this protein may be involved in receptor signaling in homeostasis and innate immunity, and during inflammatory responses [29,32]. Some studies have revealed that PSP is more accurate, with higher sensitivity and specificity than conventional inflammatory biomarkers (CRP, PCT, and IL-6), with levels below 20 ng/mL in healthy individuals[29,33,34], although more in-depth studies are needed to establish clinically relevant ranges and to confirm its diagnostic value in sepsis[35]. Despite the clinical value of simultaneously detecting several markers to simplify and accelerate diagnosis, most reported biosensing approaches focus on single-analyte detection and lack multiplexed optimization.

Our direct sensing approach uses specific antibodies immobilized on the same biosensor chip, enabling the simultaneous detection of all four biomarkers. The device, with a limit of detection (LOD) of 3×10^{-6} RIU and a sensitivity of 3490 nm/RIU , has a performance closely matching our previously validated single-channel plasmonic system. This enables

simultaneous discrimination of the multiple analytes and reaches LOD in the low ng/mL range for all four biomarkers. We demonstrate its application by detecting the panel of critical inflammatory biomarkers—CRP, PCT, IL-6, and PSP—in 10% human serum. The biosensor device delivers results under 20 minutes, emphasizing its potential for efficient and rapid diagnostics in complex human samples.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemical and biological reagents

Reagents for carboxylic acid activation (N-(3-dimethyl aminopropyl)-N'-ethyl carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) and N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide (sulfo-NHS) were provided by TCI Europe N. V. (Zwijndrecht, Belgium). Alkanethiols HS-C11-(EG)6-O-CH₂-COOH (COOH) and HS-C11-SulfoBetaine (Sulfo) were obtained from ProChimia Surfaces (Gdynia, Poland). Human serum was provided by Sigma-Aldrich/Merck (Steinheim, Germany). Recombinant human C-reactive protein (CRP), monoclonal IgG antibody against CRP (anti-CRP), monoclonal IgG antibody against interleukin-6 (anti-IL6), and CRP free serum (free-serum, containing < 20 ng/mL of CRP according to supplier specifications) were acquired from HyTest (Turku, Finland). Monoclonal IgG antibodies against procalcitonin (anti-PCT) and human IL-6 recombinant protein were obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Barcelona, Spain). Recombinant human procalcitonin (PCT), recombinant human REG-1-alpha (PSP), and monoclonal IgG antibody against PSP were provided by RayBiotech (Peachtree Corners, USA).

2.2. Multichannel plasmonic biosensor device

The multichannel plasmonic device is based on the Kretschmann attenuated total reflection (ATR) configuration and operates with a fixed incidence angle ($\theta=70^\circ$). The gold chip (coated

with 49 nm Au / 1 nm Ti, 20 mm x 20 mm) is horizontally clamped between the trapezoidal glass prism (refractive index, $n = 1.52$) and the flow cell. A polarized light (a collimated halogen light set in TM polarization) reaches the sensor chip through the prism coupling, generating an evanescent field on the sensor surface. The reflected light is collected by a fiber coupled to a CCD spectrometer (Flame series, Ocean Optics, Inc., USA.). The flow cell is connected to a microfluidic system consisting of a syringe pump (NE-1000, New Era Pump Systems, Inc., USA) with an adjustable flow rate, and a manually operated six-port injection valve incorporating a storage loop (500 μL total volume). The microfluidic cell is attached to a motorized linear stage consisting of a motorized actuator connected to a stepper motor (T-Cube DC Servo Motor Controller, Thorlabs, Inc., USA) that allows precise positioning of the different channels (X-axis movement) defined by the microfluidic flow cell. **Figure 1A** shows a rendered image of the device. The flow cell includes a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) slab that defines four sensing areas (i.e., four flow channels, Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, and Ch4) and an external polymeric cover to facilitate the delivery of liquid solutions. The design is based on a 1:4 inlet:outlet configuration through symmetric splitting of the channels. The four outlets are connected to adjustable flow restrictors to ensure constant and homogenous flow rates among the four channels. A total sample volume of 500 μL is injected and evenly distributed among the four channels, resulting in 125 μL per channel. Dedicated custom readout software (LabVIEW, National Instruments Corp., USA) has been designed to track the plasmonic reflectance spectra and plot the shift ($\Delta\lambda$, nm) of the plasmon resonance minimum (λ_{SPR}) in real-time (**Figure 1B**) for the four channels, and to control the motorized stage to move sequentially among the channels to perform the data acquisition. The reflectance spectra are acquired every 1 ms integrating over 300 consecutive spectra for each channel. The shifted position of the λ_{SPR} can be monitored in real-time via a polynomial fit using the readout software, as shown in **Figure 1C**, for each channel ($\Delta\lambda_1$, $\Delta\lambda_2$, $\Delta\lambda_3$, and $\Delta\lambda_4$). (Bio)chemical

interactions occurring at the sensor surface generate variations of the local refractive index (n , from n_1 to n_2), which correlates with the minimum wavelength displacements ($\Delta\lambda$). λ_{SPR} is directly related to mass changes at the sensor surface resulting from binding events on the sensor surface (higher n , positive wavelength shift) or desorption events (lower n , negative wavelength shift). The software displays the average spectrum and the $\Delta\lambda$ for each channel only after completing the acquisition and processing of all four channels, which takes approximately 20 seconds. The bulk sensitivity of the multichannel plasmonic device was determined by injecting hydrochloric acid solutions (HCl) at different concentrations (ranging from $n=1.33313$ to $n=1.33674$).

2.3. Microfluidic fabrication

The microfluidic network employed for real-time measurements is fabricated on a PDMS slab, with dimensions for each microchannel measuring $6000\ \mu\text{m}$ (L) x $2500\ \mu\text{m}$ (W) x $500\ \mu\text{m}$ (D) and a distance between the channels of $4000\ \mu\text{m}$. A master mold with the defined features was fabricated using an Anycubic Photon D2 resin 3D printer (Shenzhen Anycubic Technology Co., Ltd., China) for the fabrication of the PDMS layer. A polymeric cover was designed to encapsulate and attach the PDMS, clamp the plasmonic chip to the prism and the optical stage, and facilitate the tubing connections to deliver the liquids to the chip (**Figure 1A**).

An incubation chamber was designed for the biofunctionalization of the sensor chip with different antibodies for each sensing channel. The chamber consists of a $6\ \text{x}\ 6\ \text{cm}^2$ structure with a $4\ \text{x}\ 4\ \text{cm}^2$ lid and a PDMS slab with four enclosed channels ($50\ \mu\text{L}$ volume each), functioning as four small rectangular wells or compartments that match the dimensions and location of the four channels in the PDMS flow cell. The chamber dimensions are designed to ensure precise alignment and secure placement of the chip at its base. The lid tightly seals the sensor chip against the PDMS, with pressure applied by four screws. The top of the closed

chamber features eight openings, two per channel, enabling liquid injection and removal via mini luer-to-pipette adapters. The openings allow the addition of liquids with pipettes or through coupling syringes with adequate adapters. Stopper plugs can be used to seal inlets and outlets to minimize evaporation during incubation reactions (**Figure S1**).

2.3. Plasmonic sensor chip biofunctionalization

The gold sensor chips were fabricated by electron beam deposition (AJA International Inc. ATC-8E, Orion, USA). Before the functionalization, the chips were cleaned by sequential immersion in different solvents of increasing polarity (i.e., acetone, ethanol, and Milli-Q water) and heated sonication (65°C for each solvent) for one minute. The chips were dried with N₂ flow and placed inside a UV/Ozone Procleaner Plus (BioForce Nanosciences, Inc., USA) for 20 minutes. After the cleaning procedure, the chips were chemically modified through the formation of a mixed self-assembled monolayer (SAM) with a solution of thiols HS-C11-(EG)₆-O-CH₂-COOH (named here as COOH) and HS-C11-SulfoBetaine (named here as Sulfo), 1 mM (ratio COOH:Sulfo 3:7). The SAM formation was achieved by immersing the chips in the ethanolic thiol solution and heating at 40°C for ten minutes. Finally, the sensor chips were incubated overnight at room temperature. The chips were rinsed with ethanol and water and dried with N₂ flow.

The *in-situ* biofunctionalization (with the sensor chip positioned on the setup and immobilizing the same antibody in all channels, **Figure S2A**) was performed under a continuous flow of Milli-Q water (input flow from the syringe pump of 80 µL/min). The carboxylic groups were first activated as carbodiimide esters by flowing a mixed solution of EDC/NHS (0.2 M/0.05 M) in MES buffer 0.1M pH 5.5 at 20 µL/min per channel. Subsequently, an antibody solution (20 µg/mL in MES buffer 0.1M pH 5.5) was injected at 20 µL/min. The remaining unreacted carboxylic groups on the sensor surface were then

deactivated with an injection of ethanolamine (EA) solution (1M pH 8.0) for 2 minutes. Finally, the sensor chip was kept under a continuous flow of PBST buffer (PBS 10 mM + 0.05% Tween 20, pH 7.4) at 20 μ L/min.

The *ex-situ* biofunctionalization was performed in the incubation chamber that allows for individual immobilization in each channel, enabling the use of up to four different antibodies in each compartment (**Figure S2B**). The four compartments (channels) were first incubated with EDC/NHS (activation for 40 minutes), before rinsing with Milli-Q water, followed by overnight incubation at 4°C with the antibody solutions (20 μ g/mL, 50 μ L in each compartment). The antibodies employed were anti-CRP, anti-IL6 and anti-PCT in MES 0.1 M pH 5.5, and anti-PSP in Acetate buffer 10 mM pH 4.5, respectively. After overnight incubation, the chip was rinsed with water, incubated with the blocking EA solution (1M pH 8.0) for 2 min, and finally rinsed with MilliQ water. The biofunctionalized chip was carefully dried with N₂ flow, removed from the incubation chamber, and used right away by directly positioning it in the optical device and clamped with the flow cell for biosensing experiments.

2.4. Biosensing protocol

The detection of each biomarker was performed over the antibody-coated plasmonic sensor chips by direct capture (i.e. direct immunoassay). Different solutions of each biomarker (CRP, PCT, IL-6, and PSP) at several concentrations (CRP and IL6: 0 – 1000 ng/mL; PCT and PSP: 0 – 3000 ng/mL) prepared with the same running buffer, PBST buffer, were injected (total volume sample of 500 μ L), and monitoring the interaction in real-time (input flow from the syringe pump of 80 μ L/min, i.e. \approx 20 μ L/min per channel). The shift in the λ_{SPR} was considered after signal stabilization once all the sample had passed through the flow cell and the running buffer was again flowing through the biosensor (\approx 1200 s). Duplicate measurements were performed in all cases and calibration curves were generated for each protein in standard buffer

(PBST) and diluted serum (10% of CRP-free serum). For the multiplex detection, the four different antibodies were immobilized: channel 1: anti-CRP; channel 2: anti-IL6; channel 3: anti-PCT; and channel 4: anti-PSP. A 20 mM NaOH solution was injected for 30 seconds to disrupt the antibody-biomarker interactions and regenerate the sensor surface for subsequent binding.

2.5. Data statistical analysis

All data were analyzed using the Origin 2018 software (OriginLab Corp., USA) and GraphPad Prism 8 (GraphPad Software Inc., USA). Calibration curves were obtained by evaluating different concentrations of each biomarker. The mean sensor signal ($\Delta\lambda$) of duplicates or triplicates and its standard deviation (SD) were plotted versus the corresponding biomarker concentration. The data were fitted to non-linear regression curves (one site specific binding for calibration curves in buffer and one site binding with specific and nonspecific component for diluted serum). The LOD for each biomarker was calculated as the concentration corresponding to three times the standard deviation (SD) of a blank solution (i.e. corresponding buffer).

2.6. Recovery study with blind samples in serum

The biosensor performance was evaluated in terms of apparent recovery (AR%) capabilities by measuring blind samples (S1 – S8) in the working range for each biomarker. The blind samples were prepared by spiking 10% of serum with different biomarker concentrations. Single and mixed samples of different biomarkers were prepared and analyzed with the biosensor. Concentrations were determined by interpolating the signal obtained from the calibration curves generated for diluted serum. The AR values were determined by the following equation:

$$AR (\%) = \frac{[\text{Protein}]_{\text{measured}}}{[\text{Protein}]_{\text{spiked}}} \times 100$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Design and performance evaluation of the multichannel plasmonic biosensor

The developed plasmonic biosensor involves a four-channel configuration enabling parallel biosensing across multiple channels (**Figure 1A**). The optical configuration, which involves a reflection arrangement at a fixed angle of incidence (70°) is compatible with both thin-film metallic nanolayers and metallic nanostructures like gold 80-100 nm nanodisks or nanodimers[36,37]. The prototype employs spatial multiplexing, where each sensing channel is measured sequentially using a motorized linear stage that moves the optical platform containing the plasmonic chip clamped to the microfluidics, controlling the detection zone along the X-axis. We have combined the effectiveness of this optical design with customized microfluidics that simplify and minimize the required microfluidic instrumentation. The microfluidic channels were designed with dimensions of $6000\ \mu\text{m}$ (L) \times $2500\ \mu\text{m}$ (W) \times $500\ \mu\text{m}$ (H), considering the need for a robust 1:4 symmetrical flow-splitting configuration compatible with multiplexed sensing (see **Figure 1**/**Figure 2**). Although lower channel heights are generally more favorable for improving mass transport and capture efficiency in protein detection, a $500\ \mu\text{m}$ height was selected, based on fabrication reliability, as lower heights ($200\text{--}300\ \mu\text{m}$) led to structural deformation and poor reproducibility during PDMS molding and bonding due to the wide and long channel geometry. This configuration also guarantees continuous and homogenous flow among the channels within the required flow rates for biosensing measurements ($10\text{--}20\ \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ per channel; $40\text{--}100\ \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ input flow from the syringe pump) without significant air bubble generation. Flow restrictors at the outlets were also included to increase the robustness of the device for continuous evaluation. The microfluidics cover has been designed for convenient introduction, alignment, and exchange of the plasmonic chips, enabling durability and a user-friendly operability of the device. The

microfluidic design was evaluated to ensure homogeneous liquid distribution across the four channels. Flow reproducibility was confirmed under a total input rate of 80 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, yielding consistent individual flow rates around 18.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ ($\sim 18.45 \mu\text{L}/\text{min} \pm 0.59 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$), in line with the requirements of our biosensing experiments and supporting the system's suitability for multiplexed analyses. The integration of all the components allows the sequential monitoring of the four sensing channels, generating individual resonance spectra and tracking of the λ_{SPR} (see **Figure 1B,C**).

Figure 1. (A) (left) 3D render of the multichannel SPR device (optical illumination and detection system with a motorized stage, stepper motor, and prism-coupled microfluidic flow cell); (right) motorized stage and flow cell detailing the sample inlet and outlet and its split into four channels. (B) Spectra (photon counts vs. wavelength, nm) showing wavelength shift of the resonance peak ($\Delta\lambda$) resulting from refractive index changes ($n_2 > n_1$). (C) Representative picture of the acquisition software for real-time monitoring of the wavelength shift (wavelength, nm, vs. time, s) for the four channels (each channel immobilized with a different antibody).

Figure 2. A) A microfluidics branched design featuring one inlet and four outlets. (B) PDMS microfluidic slab fixed below the polymeric cover. (C) Color dye injection in the microfluidic cell clamped to a glass slide so highlight the synnetrical branched design.

For thin film metallic chips, the plasmonic spectra show a reflectivity dip at $\lambda_{SPR} = 685$ nm in all the channels, as shown in **Figure S3**. The calculated full width at half maximum (FWHM) was also similar (53.08 ± 0.27 nm) for the four channels: 53.33 nm, 52.92 nm, 53.30 nm, and 52.78 nm respectively. These parameters reflect the uniformity and reproducibility within the gold plasmonic chip and the optical setup, and consistency in the experimental conditions, with a homogeneous delivery of the solution to the four sensing channels (i.e. water). This was confirmed with real-time measurements when bulk sensitivity experiments were performed to determine the setup resolution and sensitivity, which is limited by noise in the system. The fitting process resulted in baselines with equal and very low noise for the four channels with an average noise of the four channels of 0.00343 ± 0.00045 nm (Ch 1= 0.00316 nm, Ch 2= 0.00395 nm, Ch 3= 0.00297 nm, and Ch 4= 0.00365 nm). This homogeneity was also observed

in the real-time evaluations. **Figure 3A** shows wavelength shifts obtained while solutions with different refractive index were flowed over the sensor surface. The relationship between the λ_{SPR} and the refractive index change is illustrated in **Figure 3B**, and it is possible to observe the good linearity ($R^2 > 0.99$) and sensitivity (slope of 3489.5 ± 49.8 nm/RIU) obtained across the four channels. According to the slope and the setup noise, the LOD was estimated to be $2.9 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{-6}$ RIU. The values were analogous to the ones obtained with a single-channel prototype, which exhibits a noise of 0.00269 nm and a LOD 2.9×10^{-6} RIU (slope=2706.5 nm/RIU), confirming the good performance of the multiplexed plasmonic device. The obtained parameters match the performance reported for similar or conventional plasmonic devices with multiplexed capabilities previously described in the literature (10^{-5} to 10^{-8} RIU) [26,38].

Figure 3. (A) Real-time sensorgrams obtained for the four channels for different concentrations of HCl. (B) Relationship between the λ_{SPR} shift ($\Delta\lambda_{\text{SPR}}$) and the refractive index change (Δn) for each channel. The linear fitting showing the slope (sensitivity) is included.

3.2 Biosensing performance of the multiplex plasmonic device

The biosensing performance of the multichannel device was assessed by increasing the number of immobilized antibodies. To evaluate the reproducibility among the different channels (i.e. interchannel reproducibility) an immobilization in real-time (in-situ within the biosensor) was carried out with anti-CRP. **Figure S4** shows the three-step real-time immobilization of anti-

CRP (20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) across the four channels. The performance of the four channels demonstrates their uniformity, with minimal variability observed between channels, as indicated by a low coefficient of variation (CV) of 2.2%. Moreover, when different concentrations were analyzed, the target (CRP) detection was similar in all the channels as can be appreciated by the fitted calibration curve (one-site specific binding) (**Figure 4A**). The average LOD for all channels was 4.8 ± 1.2 ng/mL, similar to previous results employing a single-channel plasmonic sensor with both the same conditions (LOD of 2.5 ng/mL, data not shown) and better than other biofunctionalization strategies [39].

To ensure the selective immobilization of different receptors in each channel, the biofunctionalization must be done outside the biosensor as the bifurcated fluidic system delivers a single solution to all four channels. Conceptually, this *ex-situ* immobilization approach is also preferable, as it aligns with the practical and commercial perspective of implementing single-use disposable cartridges in clinical settings, simplifying operation and ensuring reproducibility while minimizing the risk of cross-contamination. Thus, an *ex-situ* immobilization was performed adapting to the optimal conditions using an incubation chamber designed for this purpose. The use of the same antibody (anti-CRP) in the four channels confirmed the same analytical characteristics of the fitted calibration curve, with slightly lower biosensor responses but with similar LOD across the four channels (average LOD of 3.1 ± 0.9 ng/mL) and similar low variability (see **Figure 4B**) The results obtained for *ex-situ* and *in-situ* assays reveal similar characteristics for both, confirming excellent reproducibility of both protocols with the calculated LOD for the *ex-situ* protocol slightly lower than the LOD obtained using the *in-situ* assay. While *in-situ* immobilization may offer certain benefits during the optimization process, as it can be monitored in real-time, *ex-situ* immobilization may provide improved sensitivity and lower detection limits [40–42]. This is primarily because it enables more efficient bioreceptor coupling through longer and more controlled incubation

steps, resulting in higher immobilization yields and more homogeneous surface coverage. In addition, *ex-situ* functionalization is especially well suited for multiplex biosensing, as it allows independent and precise functionalization of each sensing area with different bioreceptors, which is less practical to achieve with *in-situ* methods in split microfluidic designs. For these reasons, we adopted the *ex-situ* approach in subsequent experiments, using a dedicated incubation chamber for reproducible and scalable sensor preparation (see **Figure S2B**).

Figure 4. (A) Calibration curves in standard buffer (PBST) for CRP with the immobilization performed *in-situ* (solid lines) and *ex-situ* (dashed lines). Sensor response, $\Delta\lambda$, represents the mean \pm SD of duplicate measurements. (B) Average LOD for the four channels following the *in-situ* (blue) and the *ex-situ* (grey) immobilization. Inset graph shows the individual LOD determined for each channel.

To assess the multiplex capability of the multichannel biosensor, a preliminary evaluation was conducted by preparing a biofunctionalized chip with only two bioreceptors (anti-CRP in Ch1 and Ch3, and anti-PCT in Ch2 and Ch4). When exposed to CRP or PCT (500 ng/mL), only the corresponding channels showed clear specific binding signals, remaining close to zero in the others (**Figure 5A,B**). Mixed solutions of CRP and PCT at different concentrations (250–1000 ng/mL) confirmed simultaneous detection without cross-reactivity, as each biosensor channel detected its target biomarker (**Figure 5C**). The results, summarized in **Figure 5D**, demonstrate the biosensor's selectivity, reproducibility, and capability to monitor two biomarkers independently and simultaneously within the same flow cell and sample.

Figure 5. Real-time sensorgrams for (A) 500 ng/mL of CRP, (B) 500 ng/mL of PCT, and (C) 500 ng/mL of CRP and 500 ng/mL of PCT, over the sensor chip biofunctionalized with anti-CRP (20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) in Ch1 and Ch3; and anti-PCT (20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) in Ch2 and Ch4. Time of sample injection (on) and of switching solution to regeneration (off) are indicated with arrows. (D) Detection signals ($\Delta\lambda$) obtained in each channel for different CRP and PCT concentrations (250, 500, and 1000 ng/mL).

After these positive results, we expanded the analysis to the four specific antibodies and the detection of the other inflammatory biomarkers. The results obtained in the standard buffer are summarized in **Figure 6A-D**. Standard samples containing individual biomarkers were injected in the multiplexed chip, generating calibration curves for the corresponding channels (CRP, IL-6, PCT, and PSP, in Ch1–4, respectively) reaching a LOD in the low ng/mL in all cases. These values demonstrate the effectiveness of our multiplex plasmonic biosensor in capturing, detecting, and quantifying four inflammatory biomarkers simultaneously, even in the presence of one another. The use of a mixed SAM containing sulfobetaine moiety, a zwitterionic structure that produces a low fouling surface [43,44], and the affinity provided by the

antibodies themselves, resulted in the generation of very specific signals, corroborated by negligible cross-reactivity among the different biomarkers in the other channels. **Figure S5** shows representative sensorgrams for the four biomarkers at high concentrations (CRP (500 ng/mL), IL-6 (500 ng/mL), PCT (1250 ng/mL), and PSP (2000 ng/mL)). Marginal nonspecific binding was observed in the PSP assay, with similar values regardless of the non-target biomarkers and their concentration. This could be attributed to intrinsic differences in the anti-PSP properties which might make it more prone to nonspecific adsorptions depending on their charge and variable region. Additionally, the optimal immobilization conditions for this antibody, which differed from those employed for the other three antibodies (due to the use of a different buffer) may have also altered antibody conformation and stability, facilitating weak interactions with other biomarkers. The stability of the biofunctionalized sensor chip for reuse was assessed through regeneration cycles using basic conditions to disrupt antibody–biomarker interactions. A 20 mM NaOH solution effectively dissociated these interactions across all four antibody/biomarker assays, enabling the simultaneous reuse of the multiplexed chip. Under these conditions, the biosensor remained functional for 8 to 13 regeneration cycles, depending on the bioreceptor, without compromising antibody integrity or altering detection signals and overall assay performance (**Figure S6**).

Figure 6. Calibration curves in standard buffer (PBST) for the four biomarkers obtained with the multiplex biofunctionalized sensor chip. (A) CRP in channel 1, (B) IL-6 in channel 2, (C) PCT in channel 3, and (D) PSP in channel 4. The nonspecific signals obtained in the other three channels for each concentration are also shown. Each value corresponds to the mean \pm SD of duplicate measurements. For all graphics: channel 1 (**black**), channel 2 (**red**), channel 3 (**blue**), and channel 4 (**green**).

3.3. Multiplexed biosensing in serum

To assess the performance of the multiplex plasmonic biosensor as a reliable diagnostic tool for inflammatory biomarkers monitoring in patient samples, we investigated the influence of serum on the quantification accuracy for the analysis of CRP, IL-6, PCT, and PSP. We employed CRP-free human serum (free-serum) as this protein is present in the blood of healthy individuals at relatively high concentrations (< 3 mg/L). This was reflected in the high signal obtained over anti-CRP immobilized chip when conventional serum was evaluated, which was drastically reduced with free-serum (see **Figure S7**). Dilution of the free-serum ten-fold in the assay buffer (PBST) effectively reduced the remaining nonspecific signals by up to 90%, with

similar results even at higher dilution factors, such as 100-fold (1%). These background signals were consistent across the four channels for free-serum 10% ($\Delta\lambda = 0.07 \pm 0.04$ nm, average of four channels), and comparable to those obtained in our previously developed single-channel plasmonic sensor ($\Delta\lambda = 0.08 \pm 0.05$ nm, data not shown). According to these results, the free-serum diluted 1:10 in PBST, without any additional blocking step, was employed for further experiments to evaluate the detection capability for each biomarker assay in the multiplexed biosensor (see **Figure S8** for representative real-time sensorgrams for several CRP concentrations). **Figure 7A-D** shows the analytical curves for CRP, IL-6, PCT, and PSP, in 10% of free-serum, respectively. This study confirmed the good performance exhibited by the proposed biosensor with LOD of 3.5 ng/mL for CRP (from 150 to 750 ng/mL), 6.3 ng/mL for IL-6 (from 100 to 500 ng/mL), 35.8 ng/mL for PCT (from 500 to 2000 ng/mL), and 13.3 ng/mL for PSP (from 500 to 2000 ng/mL). Slightly better LODs were observed for CRP, IL-6, and PSP biomarkers in diluted serum compared to PBST, while the LOD for PCT worsened. In the specific case of PSP detection, the non-specific binding observed under buffer conditions was eliminated when using diluted serum, highlighting the significant impact of matrix composition on assay specificity. These results may be attributed to the presence of albumin in serum, which can influence protein structure and conformation, as well as reduce non-specific binding through surface blocking and electrostatic shielding. Depending on the nature of the interactions involved, this effect may either enhance or impair binding affinity, ultimately impacting the detectability of the target analyte [45,46]. Nevertheless, all four biomarkers maintained a LOD within the low ng/mL range.

Figure 7. Calibration curves in 10-fold dilution factor of free-serum for the four biomarkers. (A) CRP in channel 1, (B) IL-6 in channel 2, (C) PCT in channel 3, and (D) PSP in channel 4. The nonspecific signal values obtained from the non-target markers are also shown. Each signal corresponds to the mean \pm SD of duplicate measurements. Channel 1 (**black**), channel 2 (**red**), channel 3 (**blue**), and channel 4 (**green**). The traced line (----) indicates the average background signal for free-serum 10%.

The recovery capability of the multiplexed plasmonic biosensor for quantifying inflammatory biomarkers was preliminarily assessed by spiking free-serum biomarkers with varying protein concentrations. All samples included CRP, as this protein is present at high concentrations in real serum and better mimics plasma conditions in patients. The samples also contained different concentrations of the other proteins (IL-6, PCT, and PSP), which are typically found at levels several orders of magnitude lower than CRP. Eight blind samples (concentrations unknown to the researcher performing the analysis) were prepared (S1-S8), covering the working range of each biomarker assay. The samples were diluted 10-fold and directly measured with the plasmonic biosensor. The responses were monitored in real-time,

and the results were interpolated in all the calibration curves. The results are summarized in **Figure 8** and **Table S1**.

Figure 8. Apparent recovery studies with blind mixture samples containing CRP (black), IL6 (red), PCT (blue) and PSP (green) biomarkers. Linear regression fits comparing the real concentration of the biomarker in the sample with the measured values obtained with the multichannel biosensor are shown. The dashed line represents a perfect correlation between both (slope=1).

A remarkable correlation was observed for IL-6 and PSP, with a strong slope close to unity in both cases and a good coefficient of determination (R^2). In the case of PSP, while all the AR% values were within an acceptable range for analytical validation (87–105%), the IL-6 preliminary validation indicated a slight overestimation with some discrepancies (see Table S1). For PCT an overall underestimation was observed (i.e. AR% between 66–102.6%), especially true for concentrations above 1500 ng/mL. Similarly, the CRP detection also revealed underestimated values, with a correlation slope of 0.631 for blind samples prepared at concentrations within the assay dynamic range. Although the nonspecific adsorption component of free-serum was accounted for in the calibration curve fitting, the observed underestimation may be attributed to additional matrix effects arising from protein interactions with the biofunctionalized surface.

Overall, the results demonstrate the usefulness of the multiplexed biosensor device for simultaneous monitoring of four different inflammatory biomarkers within the same sample.

In the context of acute inflammation, the diagnosis of severe conditions like sepsis remains challenging, as no single biomarker serves as a definitive gold standard. The clinical levels of multiple biomarkers typically increase in patients with acute infections compared to those with noninfectious systemic inflammation. **Table 1** summarizes the clinical ranges of our measured biomarkers in healthy individuals compared with those undergoing severe sepsis. According to this and based on our serum dilution results, the multiplexed plasmonic biosensor is suitable for detecting CRP (with a LOD three orders of magnitude better than required) and PSP via our direct binding approach. The sensitivity achieved for PCT and IL-6, however, would need to be improved to match the more demanding clinical requirements.

Table 1. Selected clinical biomarkers for sepsis detection

Biomarker	Category	Concentration in healthy individuals ng/mL	Concentrations in severe sepsis ng/mL	Sample type	Ref.
CRP	Acute phase protein	< 3000	> 50000	Whole blood, serum, urine	[14,15]
IL-6	Pro or anti-inflammatory cytokine	< 0.025	> 3	Whole blood, serum, CSF	[14,15,47]
PCT	Acute phase protein	< 0.05	> 2	Whole blood, serum	[14,15]
PSP	Acute phase protein	< 20	> 177	Whole blood, serum	[29,31,48,49]

CRP: C-reactive protein; IL-6: Interleukin-6, PCT: Procalcitonin; PSP: pancreatic stone protein; CSF: cerebrospinal fluid.

Numerous examples have already been reported on the individual detection of CRP, IL-6 and PCT with a multitude of sensing mechanisms, including electrochemical [50–52] and plasmonic-based systems [53–55] demonstrating remarkable sensitivity, particularly through complex or enhanced assay formats. CRP has been widely detected reaching different detectabilities [56,57], some of them with excellent sensitivity down to 5 fg/mL, for example using aptamer-antibody sandwich SPR sensors enhanced with quantum dots [58]. PCT detection has largely relied on electrochemical sensors, achieving sub-pg/mL LODs [59–61]. IL-6 detection has also been reported with electrochemical and optical biosensing [62,63] with excellent sensitivity in some cases, down to fg/mL levels [64]. However, these approaches

target solely one analyte and involve complex surface chemistry or amplification steps. In contrast, our multiplexed plasmonic platform achieves simultaneous, label-free detection of four sepsis biomarkers, including PSP, in the ng/mL range, which aligns well with clinically relevant concentrations. To our knowledge, this is the first reported plasmonic biosensor-based assay developed for the direct and sensitive detection of the PSP biomarker and its detection is rarely reported beyond commercial immunoassays (i.e. abioSCOPE® from Abionic SA, which employs fluorescence-based detection or conventional ELISA kits), highlighting the novelty and potential of our approach for early sepsis diagnostics. However, until now, they have not been combined in a multiplexed strategy for simultaneous marker detection within the same sample. Although the impact of complex matrices like serum has been previously evaluated in SPR multichannel platforms [65,66], such studies remain limited and have not addressed the specific panel of biomarkers examined here, particularly regarding specificity in the presence of multiple biomarkers within a single sample. This fact highlights the significance of our new plasmonic platform, demonstrating its potential as a powerful tool for multiplex biomarker detection in clinical samples with a single sample injection.

4. Conclusions

We have designed a practical and efficient multichannel plasmonic biosensor that provides reproducible and reliable simultaneous detection of up to four different analytes within a same sample. The compact device integrates optical illumination and detection subsystems, a motorized stage that facilitates the sequential monitoring of the different sensor channels, and a dedicated microfluidic cartridge, which has been carefully designed to facilitate the delivery of one single sample onto the different sensing areas. The microfluidic flow cell serves as the core of the sample manipulation system, enabling efficient multi-channel operation with low sample consumption (500 μ L per injection). All the subsystems are integrated and controlled

with dedicated custom software that enables routine measurement. The sensitivity and LOD (2.9×10^{-6} RIU) of the biosensor device align with other plasmonic devices operating under single analyte detection.

The potential of the platform to be used in clinical practice for sensitive detection in complex matrices has been demonstrated through the implementation of a multiplexed direct assay for the detection and quantification of four key inflammatory biomarkers related to sepsis (CRP, IL-6, PCT, and PSP) in serum samples. We optimized the assay conditions, including the customized biofunctionalization of distinct sensing areas with specific antibodies for direct and reproducible capture of each biomarker. The proposed multiplex biosensor reached good LOD in the low ng/mL range (3.5 ng/mL for CRP, 6.3 ng/mL for IL-6, 35.8 ng/mL for PCT, and 13.3 ng/mL for PSP) in diluted serum samples with negligible cross-reactivity among the antibody-coated channels. The direct and label-free format of the detection strategy and the convenient features of the motorized stage ensure the quasi-simultaneous monitoring of the four channels with a short total measurement time (20 min) necessary for POC use.

The multiplexed biosensor has been preliminary validated with blind samples containing mixtures of the different biomarkers demonstrating, good assay recovery, especially for IL-6 and PSP (AR% 103–114% and 96–105%, respectively) and for low CRP concentrations (AR% 98–118%). The biosensor assay for the four inflammatory biomarkers requires further development to improve overall apparent recovery and sensitivity in the case of IL-6 and PCT to be able to attempt clinical validation with real patient samples. Nevertheless, these promising results position our new plasmonic prototype as an attractive analytical tool for rapid, accurate, and multiplex diagnosis. With its compact and user-friendly design, this platform offers broad applicability and could be easily adapted for the analysis of other human fluids, such as plasma, urine, cerebrospinal fluid, saliva, or nasopharyngeal swabs. By adapting the microfluidics design to a disposable cartridge for convenient usage for non-technical staff, the biosensor

could be located outside research or clinical analytical laboratories. Its versatility and cost-effectiveness position this multiplexed biosensor as a complementary device for decentralized diagnosis supporting the medical community to meet rapid and reliable results for diseases requiring the tracking of multiple biomarkers for differential diagnosis and therapy adjustment.

Author contributions

Juliana Fatima Giarola: Methodology, investigation, data curation, formal analysis, validation, visualization, writing-original draft

Patricia Ramírez-Priego: methodology, investigation, data curation, validation, visualization:

M.-Carmen Estevez: Conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, project administration, supervision, validation, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing.

Laura M. Lechuga: Conceptualization, supervision, funding acquisition, writing – review & editing.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Table of Contents

A multichannel plasmonic biosensor has been developed for the simultaneous detection of up to four inflammatory biomarkers relevant to sepsis diagnostics. Its performance has been optimized, and analytical validation has been conducted for the detection in diluted serum, highlighting its potential for clinical applications